
ISOLATION, MICRO-ORGANISM PROPERTIES INVOLVED, USED AS BIO-PESTICIDES, AND THE DEGRADATION PERCENTAGE OF EACH SAMPLES

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ABSTRACT

Pesticides are extensively employed in Nigeria. Most states prohibit the application of pesticides and are banning or destroying agro-products containing harmful chemicals that are imported into their country. Microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, and viruses have been used successfully as bio pesticides. Pesticides serve a significant role in agricultural development in Nigeria by providing pesticide to farmers in order to eradicate pests and diseases. Their significance in crop production advancement is widely acknowledged. However, their highly toxic nature poses a fatal environmental risk. The current research is aimed at developing a biodegradation method to reduce the pesticide's environmental impact.

Six (6) bacterial and four (4) fungal cultures demonstrated significant ability to degrade pesticides during this study, and these cultures were identified as *Acinetobacter radioresistens*, *Pseudomonas frederiksbergensis*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Serratia liquefaciens*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Burkholderia gladioli* among bacteria and *Aspergillus niger*, *Ganoderma australe*, *Trichosporon*, *Verticillium dahliae* among fungus.

Keywords: Pesticides, Agriculture, Environment, Bacteria, Fungi.

I. INTRODUCTION

Farming has continuously been Nigeria's major industry due to its commitment to food, labor, and almost 24.14 percent contribution in public GDP. To keep up with the massive amount of Agro-production, in addition to the use of high-yielding seeds and suitable composts, a massive amount of quality pesticides has been used. Unnecessary pesticide application also causes massive amounts of pesticide to accumulate in soil and water, affecting ecological way of life and drinking water. As a result of the absorption and accumulation of these toxic chemicals, pesticides have become a significant health danger. Bioremediation, which uses microorganisms such as explicit bacterial detaches to alter contaminations to a nontoxic level, is gaining popularity in the research community since it is less expensive and can particularly achieve entire obliteration of ecological pollutants. To achieve bioremediation, certain microbial strains capable of degrading the pesticide in situ are necessary. In order to have safe farming and modern produce, in the climate, natural formulated pesticides are utilized to combat pests and pathogens. Regardless of their usefulness in increasing food yield, the widespread use of pesticides throughout the development, preparation, capacity, transport, or displaying of agricultural products might result in soil pollution. Pesticides can remain in the soil for several years after application, or for several hours, weeks or months. It's mind-boggling how much solid waste is produced during pesticide production, comprising chemical compounds used in assembly as well as residuals produced throughout the assembling/detailing procedure [1]. Just 2 to 3 percent of sprayed pesticides are effective, according to WHO statistics [2,3,4] and they are used to stop irritation, to control it, and to kill it, with the rest remaining on the field. As a result, the Residual pesticides in the topsoil poison the entire climate system. No one is immune to pesticides or the health effects that might result from exposure to them [2]. Every year, around 1 million people die or get infected as a result of pesticide poisoning [3].

Pesticides are defined as any substance or combination of substances used to control harmful irritations like aphids, weeds, as well as numerous other organisms such as nematodes, other arthropods, and vertebrates that threaten our food supply, health, or environment. To be more specific, the term pesticide refers to inorganic chemicals that interfere with the normal cycles of living things perceived to be irritants, regardless of whether they are tiny parasitic insects, morphology of microbes, weed. Some of the most common uses for pesticides are

to prevent infestations by irritants and protect crops against potential production losses or product quality degradation [1]. It is possible that these irritants inflict injury or interfere in some other way with the development or elaboration of food products, farming goods, wood products, or creature nourishment.

Furthermore, the usage of pesticides may have adverse effects on many types of life and biological systems; this will depend on the reasonableness grade of the microorganism and the pesticide [4]. Around 90 percent of pesticides used in rural areas never make it to their intended target life forms. Instead, they are dispersed in the air, soil and water. As a result, they are frequently identified in the atmosphere and on the surface. Therefore, many plant pesticides are intentionally introduced into the soil surroundings for the management of plant irritants. However, microorganisms, that results in the accumulation of their residues and compounds in soil at inadmissibly high rates [5,6]. Toxic pesticides find their way into topsoil, where they may be harmful to arachnids, nocturnal worms, parasites, microorganisms, and protozoa. Due to the fact that they influence both the structure and capacity of biological systems, microscopic organisms are essential to biological systems [7,8,9].

Microorganisms are used in bioremediation in order to eliminate or immobilize residues product [7]. It focuses on the harmful synthetic chemicals through mineralization, alteration, or modification [8]. The application of regular bioremediation in waste management dates back a long time; nevertheless, it was only in the last few decades that this practice was specifically aimed at reducing solid waste. To a lesser degree, this can be attributed with modern bioremediation and the use of microorganisms to burn through contaminants. Recent years have seen a rise in interest in the microbial biodegradation of contaminants as people search for long-term solutions to cleaning up polluted surroundings. Scientists hope to use bioremediation and biotransformation methods to take advantage of the amazing, naturally occurring ability of microbial biotransformation to degrade, transform, or accumulate a wide range of compounds.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Effect of pesticide in Nigeria

Using pesticides for a variety of purposes has resulted in a rise in pesticide contamination throughout the country. Due to a lack of data on the effects of pesticides on the Nigerian population, it is impossible to determine the actual impact on human health. It is impossible to overstate the benefits of pesticide usage, but their use raises numerous environmental issues, including as potential harm to people and other species. Insecticides and herbicides are sprayed onto non-target species, air, water, and soil, with over 98% and 95% respectively. One of the causes of water pollution is pesticide use; certain pesticides are persistent organic pollutants and contribute to contamination in soil. There are several factors that contribute to pesticide poisoning. These include the following: mishandling and inappropriate disposal of pesticides containers, the storage or handling of pesticides near edible foods, and the transportation of pesticide-treated foodstuff in the same truck or automobile. There are a number of people who come into contact with pesticides on a regular basis either accidentally or by working in the pesticide industry. These people include pesticide manufacturers and distributors as well as mixers and transporters, loaders and operators of pesticide application equipment. Since the application of pesticides is harmful to the environment, in terms of the effect on soil, water, food, human health, and animals mostly the fishes are prone to illness. The use of organic pesticides (bio-pesticides) is used to substitute the chemically synthesized pesticides.

2.2 A Brief Summary of Bio-pesticides in Nigeria.

In the early 1950s, lindane, a synthetic chemical pesticide, was introduced in Nigeria. An increase in chemical pesticides was needed to increase agricultural productivity and crop production as a result of development and population growth. As a result, the usage of pesticides skyrocketed in 1960, following the country's independence. Pesticide residues are toxic and persistent, contaminating crops, food, soil, and groundwater. As a result of this, calls have grown to phase out the pesticides made using synthetic chemicals in agriculture, and bio-pesticides are also being promoted, particularly in the developing world.

2.3 An overview of Nigeria's use of Biopesticides

Despite the fact that biopesticides have been extensively documented to be beneficial for crop protection and disease control in agriculture, biopesticide use in Nigeria remains low. As a result of Okwute's research in

Nigeria, many plant-based pesticide sources were found, analyzed and highlighted. According to the scientists, more than 30 plant species in Nigeria contain bioactive pesticides in their leaf and bark, and currently microorganism are now used for production for bio-pesticide.

2.4 Problems with pest in agriculture

Difficulty in creating food yield is caused by several insects including parasites and plant bugs, which reduce rural harvests by 20 to 40 percent every year. Insecticides played a major role in resolving these concerns. Because of the over-reliance on compound pesticides and their inevitable inappropriate use, alternatives have become increasingly important, owing mostly to natural difficulties [12]. There are currently roughly 175 dynamic synthetic chemicals in biopesticides and 700 active chemicals registered worldwide. In agribusiness and ranger service, a few outcomes of growths, microbes, and pathogens are available worldwide for the control of the pest. Biopesticides are expected to increase in speed of 10-15% for the following Ten years, compared to substance pesticides which are expected to grow at a rate of 2 to 3 percent [13,14,15]. Because they are so precise, they do not harm non-target life forms or the environment, and they can be used against pests that are resistant to conventional chemical pesticides. They are also ideal components systems in IPM because of their specificity to target pests and their safety for non-target life forms in IPM systems.

2.5 Pesticide from Organic Substances

Bio-pesticides, as characterized by the EPA, are pesticides acquired from organic sources such as animals, plants, microorganisms, and minerals. Businesses use bio-pesticides to control parasites by using microbe-based chemicals, organic pesticides, and pesticides that are supplied by plants that have been genetically modified to deliver pesticide ingredients. When it comes to farming, bio-pesticides are utilized for distinct morphological control and infection prevention along with weed and nematode management [16]. For example, biopesticides can be classified as either biochemical, PIP, or microbial pesticides, depending on the type of AI used. The results within each of these categories are diverse and have their methods of operation.

2.6 Microbial Toxin in the Production of Pesticide

Microbiological pesticides are frequently referred to as Biological Control agents (BCAs). Natural or genetically modified microorganisms are used as active ingredients in this category. Depending on the organism, the pesticide may be produced by the organism itself or by a chemical it secretes. These pesticides are more selective and less harmful than pesticides with known active ingredients. Many of the most often applied micro-biochemicals are pathogenic microorganisms. This can be found in the form of biofungicide (*Trichoderma*, *Bacillus*), bioherbicides (*Phytophthora*), or bioinsecticides (bt) [41]. Pesticides with active ingredients that are derived from microorganisms are known as "microbial pesticides" and include rickettsia, *Mycoplasma*, and *Nematodes*. These microorganisms control pests by creating poisonous metabolites specific to the pest, causing damage, or hindering the development of other microbes through competition [40]. These microorganisms control pests by creating poisonous metabolites specific to the pest, causing sickness, or hindering the development of other microbes through competition. A pesticide is produced that is particular for the organism that is causing damage to soil as well as crops. Such organism inhibits the growth of other microbes through competition or other means. For instance, insect epizootics are often caused by some infections, which are extremely prevalent. Other pathogens, on the other hand, are rare. The microbial toxins used for pesticides are as follows:

2.6.1 Bacteria

Unicellular bacteria that range in size from less than 1m to several millimeters are known as bacteria. *Bacillaceae*, *Pseudomonadale*, *Enterobacteriaceae*, *Streptococcaceae*, and *Micrococcaceae* include the majority of insect harmful bacteria. *Bacillaceae* members, in particular *Bacillus* spp., have garnered a great deal of interest as antimicrobials. Microbiological pesticides, such as bacterial biopesticides, are the most frequent. Their primary usage is as insecticides, although they can also be employed to suppress plant pathogenic bacteria and fungal growth [18]. This means they're only effective against certain species of moths and butterflies, as well as some types of fleas or mosquitos. Effectiveness is dependent on contact with the insect and, in some cases, ingestion. Bugs' digestive systems are disrupted by bacteria releasing endotoxins, which are often specific to the insect pest in question. It colonizes the plant and drives out the pathogenic species when used to control

pathogenic bacteria or fungi. About 90 percent of the biopesticide business in the United States is made up of *B. thuringiensis* (Bt) subspecies and strains. Use of Bt in agriculture, forestry and medicine has become widespread [17]. As part of the sporulation process, it produces crystallized inclusions that contain insecticidal proteins called endotoxins or Cry proteins. Because of their high explicitness and natural security, *B. thuringiensis* and Cry proteins are effective, safe, and cost-effective options in contrast to synthetic pesticides.

2.6.2 Viruses

From more than a thousand different insect species, viruses have been isolated. IV create inclusion bodies in the host cells, while NIV do not. These viruses can be further separated into PV and (GV), which create polyhedral bodies and granular bodies, respectively. NPV and CPV are two types of polyhedroses. Most commercial viral biopesticides were developed using insect viruses from the baculovirus family (Baculoviridae) [19,21,22,23]. Yet, no cases of a baculovirus causing disease in a vertebrate have been recorded. Bug-specific baculoviruses have circular, double-stranded DNA genomes of 80–180 kbp and are enclosed. In Lepidoptera (butterflies and moths), Hymenoptera (sawflies) as well as Diptera, baculoviruses have been isolated. These rod-shaped nucleocapsid particles (Latin "baculum" means "stick") are 230–385 nanometers (nm) long, and 40–60 micrometers in diameter. They can be transmitted horizontally and are highly contagious via mouth. As a result of the insect's alkaline midgut environment, the polyhedra (OBs) disintegrate and virions are released into the midgut lumen [20]. As soon as the virions penetrate the midgut cell nucleus, the virus replicates in the nuclei of tissue cells that are vulnerable to infection (fat bodies cell only). Other tissues in the hemolymph are infected by the budded virus, such as fat bodies and nerve cells. The insect larval cell infected in the second cycle of virus replication produces budded virus, but also occludes virus particles within polyhedral nuclei. Eventually, the insect becomes nearly totally a viral bag as polyhedral accumulates within it. Polyhedral is released from an infected insect at the end of its life cycle. From an initial dose of 1000 occlusion bodies, a single caterpillar may possess over 10⁹ occlusion bodies after its death [30]. For example, infected larvae display negative geotropism before succumbing to the viral infection. The environment has a role in determining the speed at which death occurs. If the conditions are right, target pests can be eradicated in 3 to 7 days and this is excellent, but they can be killed in 3 to 4 weeks if conditions are not optimum.

2.6.3 Fungi

When it comes to IPM, entomopathogenic growths are regarded as indispensable. There is a wide variety of infectious species from different kinds of parasites. There are a large range of parasite pathogenic species, including both committed and facultative microorganisms [24]. Many insect species are susceptible to the spread of fungal infections, whereas others are not. This research was carried out in the 1980s, with the goal of finding ways to control damages caused by silkworms. In 1835, Bassi developed the germ hypothesis for the first time by using a white muscardine fungus on a silkworm, which he called *Beauveria bassiana* after himself. According to Gilbert and Gill, the discovery of this silkworm illness led to the notion of utilizing insect-infecting fungus to control insect pests. Some of the world's most popular commercial goods include less than 10 different types of mushrooms. Ascomycota, Zygomycota, and Deuteromycota are the divisions of fungi, while Oomycota and Chytridiomycota were included in the earlier categorization of fungi as well. Insect-infecting fungus include around 90 genera and over 700 species, which represent all of the main groups of fungi [27,28,29]. Toxic or entomopathogenic fungi are those that kill insects by attacking their hosts and infecting them. Toxic entomopathogens enter insects mostly through the integument, although they can also enter by ingestion or injuries or the tracheal. When distributed in the environment, these fungi can cause fungal diseases in insect populations. They are a diverse genus of fungus with over 750 species. Fungus begins infecting animals by adhering to the surface of the integument where the germ tube is developed. The fungi then begin excreting enzymes, such as proteases, chitinases, quitobias, Upases, and lipoxygenases [25,26]. A specific feature in the germinative tube, the appressorium, initiates the penetration process by destroying the insect's cuticle. As soon as the fungus enters the insect, it forms hyphal bodies that spread through the hemocoel and infect the insect's muscles, fatty bodies and mitochondria. The result is that the insect will die 3 to 14 days after being infected [31]. The fungus begins to produce micelles as soon as the when an insect or large portion of the nutrients perish, have been depleted. They then infiltrate the host's internal organs. Once they have penetrated their cuticle and reached the surface, hyphae begin to produce spores under favorable climatic circumstances.

2.6.4 Nematodes

Toxic or facultative insects are parasitized by nematodes with soft bodies and lack segmentation. These parasites are prevalent in soils and use CO₂ to determine their hosts, vibration, and other chemical signals. Heterorhabditidae and Steinernematidae species have been successfully utilized in pest management programs as biological pesticides [32]. IPM systems benefit from the use of entomopathogenic nematodes since they are deemed harmless to people. Reasonably, these pesticides are pest-specific and may be applied using standard pesticide apparatus. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) pesticide registration has been waived for entomopathogenic nematodes in the United States. Personal protective equipment and re-entry limitations are unnecessary. Problems related to insect resistance are quite improbable at this time. Among entomopathogenic nematodes, the sole free-living stage is the infective juvenile (IJ) [38]. Each of these organisms is mutually linked with bacteria from the *Photorhabdus* and *Xenorhabdus* genus. Their intestinal bacteria are released into their hemocoel at this stage, along with cells of their symbiotic bacteria. An insect's hemolymph becomes a breeding ground for germs, it kills the afflicted host in around 24 to 48 hours. Even after the host has died, nematodes keep feeding on the tissue of the dead host, grow, and reproduce. It takes four juvenile stages for the nematodes to mature [33,34]. There are a lot of infectious juveniles are subsequently discharged into the atmosphere to contaminate and accumulate on new hosts for the continuity of their life cycle, depending on the resources available. Toxic fungi begin to develop micelles as soon as the insect dies and many of the nutrients have been depleted. When the right environmental conditions are met, hyphae emerge from the insect's core through its cuticle and begin producing spores.

2.6.5 Protozoa

A category of parasitic organisms known as microsporidians, entomopathogenic protozoans are a varied collection of organisms that infect invertebrates including insects. Persistent infections and general host debilitation are the results of these pathogens' host specificity and delayed action [37]. An inundative application of microbial control agents results in reduced feeding, vigour, fertility, and lifespan in insect hosts because an inundatively applied the germination of spore in the midgut and then the sporoplasm are discharges, which attacks the host's cells causing infection. This is due to the fact that very few species have had modest success [35,36]. As a biocontrol agent for grasshoppers, *N. locustae*'s usefulness is still in dispute due to the difficulties in evaluating its efficiency in the instance of a highly mobile insect. In addition to reducing European corn borer fertility, *Nosema pyrausta* kills larvae of the European corn borer as well.

III. MATERIALS AND METHOD

3.1 Sampling of soil

Two separate agricultural sectors in Nigeria provided soil samples for analysis. In Ogiyo, Ogun State, one sample was taken from a farm, while in Lagos, Ikorodu Farm Road was randomly selected since it has a long history of farming activity. Soil samples ranging in depth from 0 to 15 cm were collected, bagged, and shipped to the lab on ice, where they were kept at 4°C and analyzed. A 10-mm screening strainer was used to separate soil samples before the bacterial screening process.

3.2 Pesticide-degrading of bacteria screening and isolation

100 ml of MSYM, 10 g of soil sample was mixed, along with 25% concentrations of pesticide. Using a rotary shaker at 150 revolutions per minute and 30 degrees Celsius, samples were incubated for seven days before being moved to a new medium and cultured under the same conditions again. Cultures of bacteria were then transferred every three to four days until increasing turbidity was seen. Pipette 0.1 ml culture broth onto MSYM in addition with pesticide agar after 3-4 times of sub-culturing. Single colonies were chosen and streaked on nutritional agar (NA) with pesticide concentrations of 25, 50, and 100 ppm. To ensure proper cultivation, cultures were incubated at 30°C for four days before being moved to a warmer environment. When cultivated on NA supplemented with 25, 50, and 100 ppm of the pesticide, pesticide degrading isolates established the clear zone surrounding their populations.

Microorganisms degrade pesticides in the laboratory

Isolates of certain bacteria have been cultured for ten days on a rotary shaker at 150 revolutions per minute and 30 degrees Celsius using MSYM in addition with pesticide. Using the Lowry's technique to assess total

protein content and cell development, samples were taken every 24 hours. Using 4 ml ethyl acetate (done three times) and vacuum conditions to evaporate the culture broth until it was completely dry, the pesticide content was determined. The extract was taken and dissolved in hexane to a limit of 2 ml and analyzed by Gas chromatography electronic captured detector.

3.3 Bacterial Isolate Characterization

3.3.1 Studies on their morphology

A bacterial colony or turbidity was detected by incubating the isolates in mineral salt yeast medium laced with pesticide at 30 degrees Celsius until visible bacterial growth was seen. The morphology of Gram's stain and cells were examined under a microscope (at a resolution of 1000x) before 16S rDNA data was performed.

Fungi Isolation, Characterization, and Testing:

25 mg/l of each pesticide was added to the soil samples before they were incubated at room temperature for around two weeks the pretreatment soil samples were rinsed in refined water and permitted to stop for 30 minutes. After all the soil debris has settled down, the supernatant was decanted into a sterile test tube and serially diluted. PDA + PM was used for dilutions less than 10⁻⁶. Some fungi were found on the screen after incubation for 6-7 days. *Aspergillus* sp. was found to be the most prevalent fungus. The isolated fungal cultures were transferred to PDA slants and then tested once again to develop in presence of pesticides by cultivating them in PDA + pesticide medium, cultures displaying the highest degree of degradation were selected for future investigations.

3.3.2 Test for Bioremediation

The pesticide through bioremediation employing *Aspergillus* sp. was studied by preparing two distinct culture media in three-fold – media containing PDA and 0.5% of pesticide and media containing PDA, 0.5% of pesticide injected with *Aspergillus* spores. After that, the plates were kept in an incubator at 28°C for around 8 days.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Test was carried out appropriately and the result was shown to degrade pesticides on microorganisms in sample. The investigation shows that six (06) bacterial cultures (figure 1) were identified to demonstrate considerable capacity to carry out the degradation of specified pesticides, these cultures were designated in figure 1.

4.1 Bacteria isolation: from pesticide contaminated soil sample

Figure 1: Isolation of Microorganisms from the pesticide contaminated soil sample

Isolates	Identified cultures
B6	<i>Acinetobacter radioresistens</i>
B11	<i>Pseudomonas frederiksbergensis</i>
B12	<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>
B14	<i>Serratia liquefaciens</i>
B15	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>
B17	<i>Burkholder gladioli</i>

Note: Hussaini, Syed Zubair, Mohammed Shaker, and Mohammed Asef Iqbal. [10]

NB: (0) shows that there is no degradation

In order to determine the percentage of each microorganism that degrades a pesticide, these microbial cultures were mixed in with the pesticides and their percentages was determined.

Table 1: Shows the degradation potential results for the Pesticides

Microorganisms	Lindane	Diazinon	Malathion	Dimetoate	Igepal CO-210	Chlorpyrifos	Isoprotruron	Endosulfan	Methyl parathion
■ Acinetobactor radioresistens	0	0	1	0	0	38	0	0	0
■ Pseudomonas frederiksbergensis	0	0	9	4	0	0	0	4	10
■ Bacillus pumilus	0	0	45	37	8	15	0	0	0
■ Serratia liquefaciens	0	51	11	0	0	0	0	0	0
							0	0	1

Note: Hussaini, Syed Zubair, Mohammed Shaker, and Mohammed Asef Iqbal. [10]

NB: (0) shows that there is no degradation

The table shows the percentage of each bacteria cultures used that are used in this study to degrade the given pesticides. The zero (0) percentage show that the pesticide did not degrade from each bacterial culture.

Figure 2: Graph showing the isolation of Bacteria cultures degrading pesticide

Note: Author's Compilation

The graph shows all the six-microorganism infused with the different pesticides. Lindane and Isoprotruron shows that the all the microorganism's culture did not degrade them in the 4 cultures. One bacteria culture degrades Endosulfan having 4 percentage (Pseudomonas frederiksbergensis). Two bacteria cultures degrade Diazinon having 51percent (Serratia liquefaciens), 34 percent (Serratia marcescens). Igepal CO-210 having 8 percent (Bacillus pumilus), 2 percent (Serratia marcescens) and Methyl parathion having 10 percent (Pseudomonas frederiksbergensis), 1 percent (Serratia marcescens). Three (3) bacteria cultures degrade Dimetoate having 4 percent (Pseudomonas frederiksbergensis), 37 percent (Bacillus pumilus), 3 percent (Burkholderia gladioli) and chlorpyrifos having 38 percent (Acinetobactor radioresistens), 15 percent (Bacillus pumilus), and 8 percent (Serratia marcescens). Four (4) bacteria cultures degrade Malathion having 1

percent (*Acinetobacter radioresistens*), 9 percent (*Pseudomonas frederiksbergensis*), 45 percent (*Bacillus pumilus*) and 11 percent (*Serratia liquefaciens*).

So therefore, out of nine (9) pesticides, *Acinetobacter radioresistens* degraded two (2) pesticides with the total of thirty-nine (39) percentage and *Pseudomonas frederiksbergensis* degraded four (4) pesticides with the total of twenty-seven (27) percentage. *Bacillus pumilus* degraded four (4) pesticides with the total of one hundred and five (105) percentage, *Serratia liquefaciens* degraded two (2) pesticides with the total of sixty-two (62) percentage. *Serratia marcescens* degraded four (4) pesticides with the total of forty-five (45) percentage, *Burkholderia gladioli* degraded one (1) pesticide with the total of Three (3) percentage. This indicates that *Bacillus* spp. are very good and are highly capable of degrading pesticides and this should be improve.

4.2 Fungi isolation: from pesticide contaminated soil sample

The investigation shows that Four (04) fungal cultures (figure 4) were identified to demonstrate considerable capacity to carry out the degradation of specified pesticides, these cultures were designated in table 2.

Figure 3: Isolation of Microorganisms from the pesticide contaminated soil sample

Isolates	Identified cultures
F24	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>
F43	<i>Ganoderma austral</i>
F79	<i>Trichosporon Sp.</i>
F102	<i>Verticillium dahliae</i>

Table 2: Chart table showing the percentage pesticide degradation by the isolated cultures

Microorganisms	Pesticides									
	Lindane	Diazinon	Malathion	Dimethoate	Igepal CO-210	Chlorpyrifos	Isoproturon	Endosulfan	Methyl parathion	
■ <i>Verticillium dahliae</i>	10	0	10	0	0	64	0	8	0	
■ <i>Trichosporon sp.</i>	7	0	0	0	0	55	0	10	0	
■ <i>Ganoderma austral</i>	65	0	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	
■ <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	29	0	0	0	0	0	0	59	0	

Note: Iqbal, Mohammed Asef, and Bartakke, K. V [11]

The percentage of each bacteria culture used in this study to degrade the given pesticides is shown in the table. The zero (0) percentage indicates that the pesticide did not degrade in any of the fungi cultures.

Note: Author’s Compilation

The graph shows all the four-microorganism infused with the different pesticides. Diazinon, Dimetoate, Igepal CO-210, Isoproturon and Methyl parathion shows that all the fungi culture used did not degrade them which shows (0) percentage in all four samples. Four (4) fungi culture degrade only Lindane having 29 percent (*Aspergillus niger*), 65 percent (*Ganoderma austral*), 7 percent (*Trichosporon sp.*) and 10 percentage (*Verticillium dahaliae*). One (1) fungi culture degrade Malathion only having 10 percentage (*Verticillium dahaliae*). Two (2) fungi culture degrade Chlorpyrifos having 16 percent (*Ganoderma austral*), 55 percent (*Trichosporon sp.*), 64 percentage (*Verticillium dahaliae*) and Endosulfan having 4 percent (*Aspergillus niger*), 10 percent (*Trichosporon sp.*) and 8 percent (*Verticillium dahaliae*).

So therefore, out of nine (9) pesticides, *Aspergillus niger* degraded two (2) pesticides with the total of eighty-eight (88) percentage. *Trichosporon sp.* degraded Three (3) pesticides with the total of seventy-two (72) percentage, *Ganoderma austral* degraded Two (2) pesticides with the total of eighty-one (81) percentage and *Verticillium dahaliae* degraded four (4) pesticides with the total of ninety-two (92) percentage. This indicates that *Verticillium dahaliae* is highly capable of degrading pesticides and this should improvise.

V. CONCLUSION

Pesticides and chemical fertilizers, in increasingly high concentration, are being applied by farmers inadequately to increase agricultural yields. Which results in the contamination of water, soil, and air by pesticides and chemical fertilizers and many diseases in humans. Biodegradation that uses microorganisms to remove pollutants is the most promising, cost-effective, and efficient technology. Effective and indigenous microbial consortia play an important role in the removal of pesticides from the environment. It is possible to reduce the use of chemical fertilizer by as much as 20–30 percent by using pesticides that degrade microbial consortium. In order to use pesticide degradation on contaminated sites on a larger scale, it is necessary to use an efficient and indigenous microbial consortium.

Six bacterial cultures and four fungal cultures were isolated with some selected pesticides that were used as samples. They were able to grow in the presence of selected pesticides. Most of them were able to degrade the compounds in the culture medium. These results helps to favor the application of *Bacillus spp* and *Verticillium dihaliae* as the potential agents used for the bioremediation of polluted environments due to different pesticides.

VI. AREA OF FURTHER STUDIES

The researcher recommends that further studies on all the compounds present during the processor degradation. The identification and characteristics of these compounds which are degraded from the culture medium should be discussed further. There is no further research done on *Bacillus* spp and *Verticillium dahliae* and their mechanism processes of how they can be of use in bioremediation for cleaning up a polluted environment. Since *Bacillus* spp and *Verticillium dahliae* have the highest decomposition percentage, so therefore, the application of *Bacillus* spp and *Verticillium dahliae* should be discussed further.

Terminologies

PIP: plant-consolidated protectants

AI: active ingredient

OCP: Organo Chlorine pesticides

IV: Inclusion Virus

NIV: Non-inclusion Virus

Bt: *B. thuringiensis*

NPV: Nuclear Polyhedrosis Virus

CPV: Cytoplasmic Polyhedrosis virus

IPM: Integrated Pest Management

PV: Polyhedron Viruses

GV: Granulosis Viruses

CO₂: Carbon dioxide

(EPA): Environmental Protection Agency

VII. REFERENCE

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